

ISSUES OF CORRELATION OF LANGUAGE AND THINKING,
LANGUAGE AND CULTURE

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Annotation. This article examines the features of the relationship between the language, culture and mentality of the people, characteristic of a given language community and the problem of the relationship of culture and language with mental categories.

Key words: mentality, culture, language community, worldview, interconnection.

Recently, in linguistics, there has been a great interest in research related to the study of the features of cognitive linguistics and linguoculturology, since they simultaneously study the sphere of language, purpose and culture. So far, issues related to language and thinking, language and culture have been developed in detail.

A small number of studies related to the study of the characteristics of a particular people, which are expressed primarily in its mentality, and works specifically devoted to a systematic description of the mentality of a given people, are due, on the one hand, to the undeveloped theory and methodology of such a description, and on the other On the other hand, it is not clear which specialists in what branch of science should deal with the problem of mentality. Description and comparison of the mentality of different peoples can become the subject of a field of science that would become a joint for a number of sciences: psychology, sociology, political science, philosophy, linguistics, ethnography, communication

theory, psycholinguistics.

Since linguistic sciences are widely represented in this list, it follows that, first of all, it is linguists who should do this.

Human culture, social behavior and thinking, as you know, are not able to exist without language and outside of language. Being a means of human communication and therefore social and national in nature, the language bears the imprint of the features of the worldview, ethical and cultural values, as well as the norms of behavior characteristic of a given language community, and all this is reflected in the vocabulary of a particular language.

Mentality is the ability to perceive the world, characteristic of large human communities; it sets the features of their response to the surrounding reality and consists of knowledge, beliefs, values, stereotypes of thinking and actions that determine the specifics of people's response and behavior. This is the ability and inclination of a person as a member of society to think and act according to collective ideas.

Mentality is a way of collective thinking and activity of a particular historical society, due to its ethnic origin, cultural affiliation, type of social development and other circumstances that determine the mentality. Mentality is a general attitude or collective way of thinking that is relatively constant and based not on critical reflection or spontaneous random thoughts, but on what is taken for granted within a given group or society.

The mentality of an individual people is also based on the above categories, but has special categorical linguistic means for its expression. For the purposes of linguistic research, mentality can be represented as a frame that breaks down into subframes: language, culture, behavior, worldview. Thus, the mentality, language and culture of a particular people mutually determine and mutually express each other.

Mentality is manifested in everything that a person thinks about, what and how he evaluates, how he relates life and events. It is inextricably linked with the

national picture of the world, which is mediated in the language and reveals the peculiarities of the representation of this or that ethnic group about the surrounding reality.

National character is a kind of national coloring of feelings and emotions, ways of thinking and actions, stable and national features of habits and traditions that are formed under the influence of the conditions of material life, the features of the historical development of a given nation and manifested in the specifics of national culture.

The mental sphere (area of conceptualization) is the human cognitive space updated by various types of texts, which includes the entire array of knowledge about the surrounding world. At the same time, the linguistic meanings of words are related to certain contexts - cognitive structures or blocks of knowledge that stand behind these meanings and ensure their understanding.

Since both culture and language are connected with the mentality of the people, i.e., their worldview and worldview, it becomes necessary to comprehend the problem of the relationship of culture and language with mental categories.

The study of the culture of the people through the language, namely through the key words of a particular language, is a relatively new and promising area of modern linguistics. This direction is widely developed in numerous studies of languages, through which one can enter the cultures corresponding to these languages. It is thanks to the systemic nature of linguistic meanings that it is possible to cognize one or another ethno-cultural community underlying its mentality. In this sense, linguoculture is a way of expressing the ethnic mentality as a special vision of the world in specific chronotopic conditions of the artistic and creative existence of a particular people.

Culture, as you know, has a fairly large set of cognitive codes. But the basic code, the core of the semiotic system of any national culture is, without a doubt, the ethnic language, since it

- not just "a means of describing culture, but, above all, the iconic

quintessence of culture itself."

Culture is formed and exists thanks to linguo-creative thinking, "attached" to a certain place, time, event and experience in general. That is why the language of culture is its "leading belt", "fifth element", elements, its natural habitat, a way of symbolic organization. The world of linguistic meanings with its structure of value-semantic relations turns out to be a cultural form of the existence of cultural knowledge and a way of its functioning in the spiritual and practical activity of the people.

Each language absorbs something from the specific identity of its nation and, in turn, acts on it in the same direction. The national character is maintained, strengthened, even to a certain extent created by the commonality of the habitat, but in its essence it rests on the sameness of the natural order, usually explained by the common origin. The languages themselves, which were the instruments of this development (intellectuality), acquire such a definite character that it becomes it is easier to know the character of a nation than by its manners, customs, and deeds.

Thus, it can be assumed that in today's world the study of foreign languages is important not only in itself, but also as a means of comprehending the mentality and culture of other peoples.

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